

1 **Comparative modelling study on enantioresolution of structurally unrelated**
2 **compounds with amylose-based chiral stationary phases in reversed phase liquid**
3 **chromatography-mass spectrometry conditions**

4 Mireia Pérez-Baeza^a, Laura Escuder-Gilabert^{a,*}, Yolanda Martín-Biosca^a, Salvador
5 Sagrado ^{a,b}, María José Medina-Hernández ^{a,*}

6 ^a *Departamento de Química Analítica, Universitat de València, Burjassot, Valencia, Spain*

7 ^b *Instituto Interuniversitario de Investigación de Reconocimiento Molecular y Desarrollo Tecnológico*
8 *(IDM), Universitat Politècnica de València, Universitatde València, Valencia, Spain*

9

10 **ABSTRACT**

11 Polysaccharide-based chiral stationary phases (CSPs) are the most used chiral
12 selectors in HPLC. These CSPs can be used in normal, polar organic and aqueous-
13 organic mobile phases. However, normal and polar organic mobile phases are not
14 adequate for chiral separation of polar compounds, for the analysis of aqueous samples
15 and for MS detection. In these situations, reversed phase conditions, without the usual
16 non-volatile additives incompatible with MS detection, are preferable. Moreover, in
17 most of the reported chiral chromatographic methods, retention is too large for routine
18 work. In this paper, the chiral separation of 53 structurally unrelated compounds is
19 studied using three commercial amylose-based CSPs -coated amylose tris(3,5-
20 dimethylphenylcarbamate) (*Am1*), coated amylose tris(5-chloro-2-
21 methylphenylcarbamate) (*Am2*), and immobilised amylose tris(3-chloro-5-
22 methylphenylcarbamate) (*Am3*)-. Chiral separations are carried out using
23 acetonitrile/ammonium bicarbonate (pH = 8.0) mixtures, reversed mobile phases
24 compatible with MS detection. To provide realistic conditions for routine analysis,
25 maximum retention factors are set to 15. Retention and enantioresolution behaviour of

26 compounds in those CSPs are compared. On the other hand, to compare and describe
27 the resolution ability of these CSPs, 58 structural variables of the compounds are tested
28 to model for the first time a categorical enantioresolution (*CRs*) for *Am1* and *Am3* CSPs.
29 Discriminant partial least squares, for one response categorical variable (DPLS1) is used
30 for feature selection, modelling. The final DPLS1 models showed good descriptive
31 ability.

32

33 *Keywords:* Amylose-based chiral stationary phases. Reversed phase liquid
34 chromatography. Enantioresolution modelling and description. Discriminant partial
35 least squares. Feature selection.

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37 Corresponding authors

38 E-mail addresses:: lescuder@uv.es (L. Escuder-Gilabert), maria.j.medina@uv.es (M.J.
39 Medina-Hernández)

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41 **1. Introduction**

42 High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with chiral stationary phases
43 (CSPs) is one of the most widely used analytical techniques for the separation of
44 enantiomers of chiral compounds. Among the large number of CSPs commercially
45 available, amylose and cellulose polysaccharide derivatives coated or immobilised onto
46 the stationary support represent by far the most widely used CSPs in HPLC. This is due
47 to their broad chiral recognition capacity that confers extensive applicability for a large
48 structural diversity of compounds and compatibility with all of the most relevant
49 chromatographic mobile phase regimes: normal, polar organic and aqueous-organic
50 mobile phases [1-7].

51 Mobile phase composition with polysaccharide-based CSPs strongly modulates
52 the stereorecognition process.. Different chromatographic behaviours, even reversals in
53 the elution order of enantiomers, are observed depending on the nature and composition
54 of the mobile phase, as a consequence of changes produced in the intra-molecular
55 hydrogen bonds of the polysaccharide structure [5,6]. Selector-selectand complexes
56 formation is mediated via hydrogen bonds involving the CO or NH groups of the
57 carbamate moieties, π - π and Van der Waals interactions with the phenyl rings, and
58 steric factors [3,7]. Halogen bonds have been also described to contribute to selector-
59 selectand complexation as electrostatic interactions [4,8]. In aqueous-organic mobile
60 phases, although water can compete for hydrogen-bond interaction sites with the chiral
61 compound and the CSP, hydrophilic interactions (residing in carbamate or ester
62 moieties) and hydrophobic interactions (associated with phenyl moieties) between the
63 analytes and the polysaccharide-based CSPs exist [5-7, 9-12, 14]. In fact, the
64 combination of polysaccharide-based CSPs and aqueous-organic mobile phases has
65 proven to be useful for the separation of enantiomers [7, 9-14].

66 Aqueous-organic mobile phases are of special importance for the separation of
67 polar compounds poorly soluble in alkanes low molecular weights alcohols or
68 acetonitrile, as well as for the analysis of aqueous matrix samples such as biological and
69 environmental samples. Also, they are useful for chiral HPLC-MS detection because
70 aqueous-organic mobile phases improve the analyte ionization [11]. Unfortunately,
71 most of the additives used in reversed phase conditions to improve resolution, to control
72 the ionic strength and the pH of the mobile phase are non-volatile or suppress analyte
73 response and therefore they are incompatible with MS detection.

74 Despite the large number of analytical applications of polysaccharides-based
75 stationary phases in HPLC, the fundamental mechanisms responsible for the observed
76 chiral separations are not fully understood because of the inherent complexity of these
77 selectors. To elucidate the chiral recognition mechanism of polysaccharide chiral
78 selectors, analytical separation techniques in combination with spectroscopic techniques
79 and molecular modelling have been used [3,6,7,15-21].

80 Chemometric methods can be helpful to extract valuable information on
81 molecular recognition [22,23]. Among these, quantitative structure-property
82 relationships (QSPRs), which correlate enantioresolution-related information (retention
83 or selectivity values) with different molecular properties of compounds, are a powerful
84 option. Different QSPR studies have been reported for modelling data in
85 enantioselective chromatography using polysaccharides-based stationary phases, [22-
86 30]. These studies are usually carried out for structurally related compounds using
87 amylose and cellulose-based CSPs and normal or polar mobile phases. In these studies,
88 information about the functional groups responsible for enantioresolution is usually
89 obtained.

90 In a previous paper [31], the enantioresolution level (categorical variable) of
91 structurally unrelated basic compounds, obtained in HPLC using immobilised cellulose
92 tris(3,5-dichlorophenylcarbamate) CSP and hydro-organic mobile phases, was modelled
93 as a function of structural and physicochemical parameters of the compounds. Similar
94 studies in electrokinetic chromatography using sulfated β - and γ -cyclodextrins as chiral
95 selectors were also performed [32-33]. The parameters used in the modelling processes
96 include molecular properties obtained from a free on-line database and classical
97 topological parameters, as well as new topological parameters connected to the chiral
98 carbon (C*-parameters). Variables were selected by means of a discriminant partial
99 least squares on one single response (DPLS1) refinement process. The models obtained
100 presented adequate descriptive and predictive capacity.

101 In this work, the chiral separation of 53 structurally unrelated compounds (47
102 drugs belonging to 13 therapeutic families and 5 fungicides) is studied using three
103 amylose-based CSPs (coated amylose tris(3,5-dimethylphenylcarbamate), coated
104 amylose tris(5-chloro-2-methylphenylcarbamate) and immobilised amylose tris(3-
105 chloro-5-methylphenylcarbamate)). Chromatographic separations are carried out using
106 reversed mobile phases compatible with MS detection consisting of mixtures of
107 acetonitrile/ammonium bicarbonate buffer ($pH = 8.0$). Maximum retention factors are
108 set to 15, in order to provide realistic conditions for routine analysis. Retention and
109 enantioresolution behaviour of compounds in those amylose-based CSPs are compared.
110 On the other hand, to compare and describe the resolution ability of these CSPs, 58
111 structural and physicochemical parameters of the compounds are tested to model a
112 categorical enantioresolution (CRs) for each column. DPLS1 is used for feature
113 selection and modelling purposes. At our knowledge, this is the first time that these

114 studies have been carried out under these strict and realistic chromatographic conditions
115 and for a large dataset of structurally unrelated compounds.

116

117 **2. Experimental**

118 *2.1. Instrumentation*

119 An Agilent Technologies 1100 chromatograph (Palo Alto, CA, USA) with a
120 binary pump, an UV–visible diode array detector, a mass spectrometer equipped with
121 electrospray and atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (ESI / APCI) sources and
122 single quadrupole, a column thermostat and an autosampler was used. Data acquisition
123 and processing were performed by means of the LC/MSD ChemStation software
124 (B.04.02 SP1 [208], ©Agilent Technologies 2001-2010).

125 An Agilent Technologies 1100 chromatograph (Palo Alto, CA, USA) with a
126 quaternary pump, a UV-visible variable wavelength detector, a column thermostat and
127 an autosampler was also used. In this case, data acquisition and processing were
128 performed by means of the Chemstation software (A.09.03 [1417], ©Agilent
129 Technologies 1990–2002).

130 Prior to injection into the chromatographic system, analyte solutions were
131 filtered through disposable 0.22 µm *Nylon*® syringe filters (Análisis Vínicos, S.L.,
132 Tomelloso, Ciudad Real, Spain). Mobile phase solutions were vacuum-filtered through
133 0.22 µm Nylon membranes (Micron Separations, Westboro, MA, USA) and were
134 degassed in an Elmasonic S60 ultrasonic bath (Elma, Singen, Germany) prior to use. A
135 Crison MicropH 2000 pHmeter (Crison Instruments, Barcelona, Spain) was employed
136 to adjust the pH of the aqueous mobile phase solutions.

137

138 2.2. *Chemicals and solutions*

139 All reagents were of analytical grade. Ammonium bicarbonate, ammonia,
140 acetonitrile (ACN) and methanol (®Multisolvent, HPLC grade) were from Scharlau,
141 S.L. (Barcelona, Spain). 5 mM Ammonium bicarbonate buffer solution was prepared by
142 dissolving the appropriate amount of ammonium bicarbonate in water and adjusting the
143 pH to 8.0 with 1 M ammonium hydroxide. Ultra Clear TWF UV deionised water (SG
144 Water, Barsbüttel, Germany) was used to prepare solutions.

145 Bicalutamide, brompheniramine maleate, bupropion hydrochloride
146 carbinoxamine maleate, chlorpheniramine maleate, clemastine fumarate, clenbuterol
147 hydrochloride, doxylamine succinate, ethopropazine hydrochloride, fexofenadine
148 hydrochloride, methadone hydrochloride, methotrimeprazine maleate, nomifensine
149 maleate, orphenadrine hydrochloride, pantoprazole sodium, pindolol, procyclidine
150 hydrochloride, rabeprazole sodium, terfenadine, thioridazine hydrochloride,
151 trimeprazine hemi(+)-tartrate and verapamil hydrochloride were from Sigma-Aldrich
152 (©Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany). Atenolol, cinildipine, isoprenaline
153 hydrochloride, mexiletine hydrochloride and propranolol hydrochloride were from
154 Acros (Acros Organics, Geel, Belgium). Citalopram hydrobromide was from Tokyo
155 Chemical Industry (Tokyo, Japan). Disopyramide was from MP Biomedicals (Irvine,
156 CA, USA). Felodipine and orciprenaline sulfate were from EDQM (Strasbourg,
157 France). Hydroxyzine hydrochloride was from Guinama (Valencia, Spain). Propafenone
158 hydrochloride and terbutaline hemisulfate were from Abcam (Cambridge, United
159 Kingdom). Bambuterol hydrochloride, bupivacaine, cetirizine hydrochloride,
160 trimipramine maleate and warfarin were from Cayman Chemical Co (Ann Arbor, MI,
161 USA). Acebutolol hydrochloride, aminoglutethimide, metoprolol tartrate, mianserin
162 hydrochloride and salbutamol sulfate were from Alfa Aesar (Thermo Fisher Scientific

163 Inc., Karlsruhe, Germany). All the rest of drugs tested were kindly donated by several
164 pharmaceutical laboratories: fluoxetine hydrochloride by Alter (Madrid, Spain) and
165 mepivacaine hydrochloride by Laboratorios Inibsa (Barcelona, Spain); propanocaine by
166 Laboratorio Seid (Barcelona, Spain); timolol maleate by Merck Sharp & Dohme
167 (Madrid, Spain) and viloxazine hydrochloride by Astra Zeneca (Cheshire, UK). All
168 racemic pesticides (benalaxyl, hexaconazole, imazalil, metalaxyl, myclobutanil, and
169 penconazole) were from Dr. Ehrenstorfer GmbH (Augsburg, Germany).

170 Stock standard solutions of compounds used in this study were prepared by
171 dissolving 10 mg of the racemate in 10 mL of methanol. Working solutions were
172 prepared by dilution of the stock standard solutions using the mobile phase solution.
173 The solutions were stored under refrigeration at 5°C.

174

175 2.3. Methodology for the chiral separation of compounds

176 The experimental maximum enantioresolution (R_{Smax}) values of the compounds
177 listed in Table 1 were obtained using the following polysaccharide-based chiral
178 columns: Lux Amylose-1 (amylose tris(3,5-dimethylphenylcarbamate); 3 μ m, 150 \times 4.6
179 mm i.d.; Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA), *Am1*; Lux Amylose-2 (amylose tris(5-
180 chloro-2- methylphenylcarbamate); 3 μ m, 150 \times 2.0 mm i.d.; Phenomenex), *Am2* and i-
181 Lux Amylose-3 (amylose tris(3-chloro-5-methylphenylcarbamate); 3 μ m, 150 \times 4.6 mm
182 i.d.; Phenomenex), *Am3*. Except for warfarin, mobile phases were prepared as binary
183 mixtures of ammonium bicarbonate buffer (5 mM, pH 8) and ACN in varying
184 proportion (10-80 % in volume of ACN). For warfarin, formic acid 0.1% (v) was used
185 instead ammonium bicarbonate buffer. The mobile phase flow rate was 1.0 mL min⁻¹ in
186 all cases except when using the Lux Amylose-2. In this last column, the mobile phase
187 flow rate was 0.5 mL min⁻¹. In all of the experiences, the injection volume was 2 μ L.

188 The detection was performed in the UV at 220 nm for all the compounds, except for
189 ethopropazine, methotrimeprazine and trimeprazine whose detection was performed at
190 254 nm. The column was thermostatted at 25 °C.

191

192 2.4. Software and calculations

193 In this paper 58 structural variables of the compounds have been used (see Table
194 S1 and S2 in Supplementary Data). Most of them were taken from the online
195 ChemSpider chemical structure database [34] and were also tested in previous papers
196 [31-33]. The first nine variables (x_1 to x_7) are the so-called C^* -parameters. These
197 parameters are obtained as the count of atoms/groups bonded to the chiral carbon (C^*),
198 for instance, C^*X (C^* -heteroatoms), C^*a (C^* -aliphatic), C^*H (C^* -H) and $C^*C=O$ (C^* -
199 carbonyl), among others [32-33]. Variables x_8 to x_{15} correspond to predicted molecular
200 descriptors from ACD/Labs and ChemAxon calculations: molecular weight (MW),
201 octanol-water partition coefficient ($\log P$), hydrogen bonding acceptor (HBA) and donor
202 (HBD), minimal (z_{min}) and maximal z length (z_{max}), polar surface area (PSA), among
203 others. Variable x_{16} , the apparent $\log P$ at working pH ($\log D$), was estimated as in
204 reference [31].

205 Variables x_{17} to x_{33} correspond to molecular topological parameters predicted by
206 ChemAxon; for example, aliphatic bond account (abc), aromatic bond count (Abc),
207 bond count (bond count), ring bond count (Rbc), fused ring count (frc), hetero ring
208 count (Hrc), heteroaliphatic ring count ($Harc$), ring count (Rc) and Balaban index (Bi).
209 Finally, variables x_{34} to x_{58} are obtained as the count of atoms/groups present in the
210 entire molecule; for instance, number of oxygen (O) and fluoride (F) atoms, hydroxyl
211 (OH), tertiary amine (NR_2), ether (ROR), CH_3 groups (ACH_3) and Cl atoms (ACl)
212 bonded to aromatic rings, aromatic ring-C-aromatic (ACA) moieties, 1,2- ($A12$) and

213 1,2,3- (*AI23*) substituted aromatic rings, aromatic nitrogen (*NA*), tertiary amine in
214 aliphatic cycles (*NRC*) and sulphur aliphatic cycles (*Sc*) groups among others.

215 Discriminant partial least squares, for one response categorical variable (DPLS1)
216 models have been performed using The Unscrambler® v.9.2 multivariate analysis
217 software [35].

218 For DPLS1 modelling, categorised *Rs* (*CRs*) values (see Table 1) were used as
219 response variable (*y*). For compounds showing baseline enantioresolution ($Rs \geq 2.0$),
220 *CRs* = 1 (class-1) was assigned. The rest of compounds were assigned to *CRs* = 0 (class-
221 0). As predictor matrix (*X*), the structural variables of the compounds (see section 2.4
222 and Table S2) were used. All *y-X* data were autoscaled before DPLS1. The
223 corresponding coefficients (scaled), directly measures the importance of the variables
224 [31-33, 36].

225 Feature selection (FS) was done using a leave-one-variable-out (or sequential)
226 strategy equivalent to that used in the sequentialfs.m code available from MATLAB®
227 R2019a (Mathworks®) web site [37]. The outputs from the DPLS1 were used to
228 eliminate the worst variable on each run (the process was called FS-DPLS1). The
229 variable whose elimination provokes the highest improvement of a target indicator (*TI*)
230 function is removed for the next run. The following function (not previously reported)
231 was considered to select the variable to be eliminated each run:

$$232 \quad TI = W1 \, dD + (1-W1) \, dDcv - W2 \, mUrb - W3 \, SSclass \quad [1]$$

233 where, *W1*, *W2* and *W3* are parameters in the 0-1 range to be optimised. *dD* is the
234 lowest discriminant distance between the outputs from the two classes (i.e. the distance
235 between the lowest *y*-predicted of class-1 and the highest *y*-predicted of class-0 data
236 from DPLS1) and *dDcv* is as *dD* but for cross-validated predicted *y*-values. *mUrb* is the

237 mean of the relative uncertainty of the DPLS1 coefficients (related to the importance of
238 the variables). SS_{class} is the sum of squares for difference between predicted and actual
239 DL values for compounds (i.e. y -predicted values from DPLS1 equal or higher than the
240 lowest y -predicted of class-1 are assigned to $DL = 1$ and y -predicted values equal or
241 lower than the highest y -predicted of class-1 are assigned to $DL = 0$; otherwise, $DL =$
242 0.5 is assigned).

243 Since dD represent the lowest distance between the classes, $dD > 0$ (the two
244 groups are fully separated) can be considered an acceptable descriptive ability.
245 Moreover, $dD_{cv} > 0$ would correspond to an acceptable predictive ability. Low $mUrb$
246 (i.e. low absolute coefficient uncertainty and/or high coefficient value) values mean
247 more confidence on the model coefficients, thus more reliable variable, while low
248 SS_{class} values indicate high classification ability, both aspects indirectly increase the
249 descriptive ability of the model.

250 The parameters ($W1$, $W2$, $W3$) were optimized for each CSP, combining
251 SIMPLEX optimization, from `fminsearch.m` [38], design of experiments (DOE), from
252 `bbdesign.m` [39] and manual refinement strategies (manually varying one parameter
253 value, previously optimized, to confirm that it is the adequate one).

254

255 **3. Results and discussion**

256 *3.1. Retention behaviour and enantioresolution of compounds in amylose-based CSPs* 257 *in reversed-phase conditions*

258 The aim of this study is to explore the ability of $Am1$, $Am2$ and $Am3$ to
259 enantioseparate chiral compounds using reversed phase conditions compatible with MS
260 detection for their use in routine analysis (k value for the most retained enantiomer

261 lower than 15). Table 1 shows the chiral compounds studied, which belong to 14
262 therapeutic families: antiarrhythmic drugs, anticoagulants, antidepressants, fungicides,
263 antihistamines, local anaesthetics, analgesics, antineoplastics, β -blockers,
264 bronchodilators, calcium channel blockers, anticholinergic drugs, antipsychotic drugs
265 and proton pump inhibitors. Table S1 in Supplementary Data shows the chemical
266 structure and the molecular weight, pK_a , $\log P$ and $\log D$ (estimated at pH 8.0) values
267 for compounds under study. At working pH s, most of the compounds studied present
268 positive net charge. Cetirizine ($No = 20$) has negative net charge; and warfarin ($No = 4$),
269 fexofenadine ($No = 24$), aminoglutethimide ($No = 32$), cinildipine ($No = 44$), felodipine
270 ($No = 45$) and fungicides ($No = 12-17$) have zero net charge. Compounds studied
271 presents variable hydrophobic character ($\log D$ values ranged between -1.6 and 5.2).

272 For each analyte and CSP, the mobile phase that provided maximum R_s and k
273 <15 values was selected. Table 1 shows the maximum resolution values (R_{smax})
274 obtained for each compound and CSP together with the content of ACN in the mobile
275 phase.

276 As can be observed in Table 1, 16 compounds of the 53 studied were fully
277 resolved (30 %) and 19 were partially resolved (36 %) at least in one of the CSPs
278 studied and the reversed phase conditions assayed. *Am1* allowed the complete resolution
279 (baseline resolution) of 11 compounds whereas 16 were partially resolved. Similar
280 results were obtained for *Am3* enabling the complete and partial resolution of 11 and 14
281 compounds, respectively. The worst results were obtained for *Am2* which only allowed
282 the baseline resolution of 4 compounds while 9 remained partially resolved. Although
283 the experimental resolution values were close or higher than 1.5 for some compounds
284 (i.e. viloxazine, metalaxyl, brompheniramine, carbinoxamine and ethopropazine),
285 baseline resolution was not observed. In these cases, the quality of the separation was

286 affected by the high peak width obtained.. The best resolution values in each column
287 were obtained for mianserine ($Rs1_{max} = 8.3$; $No = 8$) in *Am1*, propafenone ($Rs2_{max} = 4.0$;
288 $No = 8$) in *Am2* and nomifensine ($Rs3_{max} = 8.4$; $No = 9$) in *Am3*.

289 Bicalutamide and rabeprazole were baseline resolved in all three columns.
290 Warfarin, bupropion, mianserin, nomifensine, benalaxyl, bicalutamide and rabeprazole
291 were completely resolved in both *Am1* and *Am3* columns; for the rest of compounds,
292 differences in enantioselectivity between *Am1* and *Am3* columns were observed,
293 indicating differences in the interactions between the compounds and the CSPs.

294 It is known that polysaccharide-based CSPs may behave either as RP-like or
295 HILIC –like stationary phases depending on compounds characteristics and separation
296 conditions, especially when using ACN mobile phases with low water contents (<30%)
297 [6-10]. In the experimental conditions assayed in this paper which include mobile
298 phases with a water content in the range 20-90% (v/v), for all compounds and CSPs,
299 typical chromatographic reversed phase behaviour was observed. The increase in the
300 water content in the mobile phase produced an increase in the retention time of the
301 compounds. Different behaviour was observed for resolution values. In most cases,
302 resolution improved as the percentage of ACN in the mobile phase decreased (retention
303 increased), as observed in Figure 1A for rabeprazole in the column *Am2*. However, for
304 other compounds, e.g. brompheniramine in *Am1* (see Figure 1B), better resolutions were
305 achieved when using higher percentages of ACN in the mobile phase for all the CSPs
306 studied. This can be due to the existence of two opposite effects: thermodynamic and
307 kinetic processes. For some compounds, resolution is mostly affected by the
308 thermodynamics of the process (separation factor increased as retention increased) ,
309 while for other compounds, the kinetics contribution (efficiency decreased as retention
310 increased) prevails over the others [5].

311 On the other hand, for the same ACN content in the mobile phase, in general
312 terms, *Am3* provided the highest k values. This behaviour might be due to the different
313 electronic features of the polymers, along with the type CSP, that is immobilised vs
314 coated [5].

315 Figure 2 shows the relationships between the logarithm of retention factors for
316 the less retained enantiomers ($\log k_1$) and their corresponding $\log D$ values for each
317 CSP. As can be observed, retention increased as hydrophobicity increased for *Am1*
318 (Figure 2A) and *Am2* (Figure 2B) columns, as expected in reversed-phase conditions.
319 Besides, a linear trend is observed for *Am1* column. In contrast, retention of analytes
320 seems to be independent of their hydrophobicity in *Am3* column (Figure 2C).

321 3.2. Structure-categorical enantioresolution relationships in amylose-based CSPs

322 In this paper, an attempt has been performed to detect the effect of the structural
323 variables of compounds on the resolution values obtained for each amylose-based CSPs
324 in the chromatographic conditions assayed. In this paper, the experimental R_s values
325 were also converted into categorised CRs values (see section 2.4 and Table 1).

326 DPLS1 modelling was selected to relate the structural data (\mathbf{X} -matrix) (see
327 section 2.4) to the $CRs1$ and $CRs3$ data (\mathbf{y} -vectors) for *Am1* and *Am3*, respectively. *Am2*
328 was not included in the analysis because the low number of class =1 data (just 4
329 compounds, see Table 1). Table 2 shows some outputs corresponding to the initial
330 DPLS1 models (all variables) and the final model after the FS-DPLS1 process for *Am1*
331 and *Am3*. For both columns, the initial DPLS1 model with 57 variables showed a poor
332 descriptive ability, since $Dd < 0$. Thus such models become risky to define the
333 importance of the variables. After an exhaustive of optimization study of the
334 coefficients in Eq. 1, satisfactory models, with a considerable reduction of the number
335 of the (irrelevant), variables were found. As can be seen in Table 2, for both columns,

336 the results after FS-DPLS1 can be used to compare the importance of the remaining
337 variables ($dD > 0$), which fits with the aim of this paper.

338 Comparing the two columns in Table 2, apparently, the results for *Am1* are better
339 (higher dD ; with similar dD_{cv} value), but the DPLS1 model is more complex (7 latent
340 variables) compared with the one for *Am3* (2 latent variables) and also in the case of
341 *Am3*, the final mean uncertainty of the selected coefficients ($mUrb$) is lower. As an
342 example, Figure 3 shows the feature selection progress in the case of column *Am1*.

343 Figure 4 shows the DPLS1 regression coefficients (scaled) for the selected
344 variables for the columns *Am1* and *Am3*. Their absolute value indicates the importance
345 of the variable to discriminate between the classes. Their sign indicates a positive or
346 negative contribution on *CRs*. As can be observed, in both cases, variables related to
347 atoms/groups bonded to the chiral carbon (C^*) or present in the entire molecule and
348 molecular topological parameters were selected. For a given compound and a given
349 CSP, the balance between positive and negative contributions determines
350 enantioresolution in that CSP.

351 For *Am1* column (Figure 4A), among the variables linked to the chiral center
352 (C^* -parameters), $C^*C=O$ is the most important variable that favours enantioresolution.
353 Additionally, the absence of heteroatoms (C^*X variable) or hydrogen (C^*H variable)
354 substituents in C^* favours enantioresolution. The presence of carbonyl groups in amides
355 ($-C(=O)NR_1R_2$), ketones ($-C(=O)-R$) and esters ($-C(=O)-OR$) linked to the chiral center
356 is of great importance in the enantiorecognition process ($C^*C=O$ variable). This is the
357 case, for example, of bupropion ($No = 5$ in Table 1), benalaxyl ($No = 12$),
358 aminoglutethimide ($No = 32$) and bicalutamide ($No = 33$). The amides have a conjugate
359 system on the atoms of O, C, N, consisting of molecular orbitals occupied by
360 delocalised electrons and therefore, selector-selectand $\pi-\pi$ interactions can exist.

361 Amides, esters and ketones are hydrogen-bond acceptors and can provide hydrogen-
362 bond interactions with the selector.

363 The presence of aromatic bonds in the molecule that favours π - π interactions
364 also favours the enantioresolution (*Abc* variable) in *Am1* column, as in the case of
365 warfarin (*No* = 4). Nevertheless, the position and nature of the substituents in the
366 aromatic ring can favour (e.g., *ACI*, *A12* and *A123* variables) or disfavour (e.g., *ACH3*,
367 *ACA*) enantioresolution. The absence of aliphatic bonds in the molecule (*abc* and *bc*
368 variables) also favours enantioresolution. On the other hand, for *Am1* column, the
369 presence of a ternary amine (hydrogen-bond acceptor) in an aliphatic cyclic group also
370 favours enantioresolution (*NRc* variable).

371 For *Am3* column (Figure 4B), $C^*C=O$ is the most important variable, among
372 C^* -parameters, that favours enantioresolution; so selector-selectand π - π interactions and
373 hydrogen-bond interactions are of utmost importance for chiral separation. Moreover,
374 the absence of heteroatoms (C^*X variable, as in *Am1* column) or aliphatic (C^*a
375 variable) substituents in C^* favours enantioresolution. As in the case of *Am1* column,
376 aromatic bonds (*Abc* variable) favours enantioresolution. Additionally, the presence of
377 fused rings (*frc* variable) also improves resolution, as in the case of mianserin (*No* = 8),
378 nomifensine (*No* = 9), pantoprazole (*No* = 52) or rabeprazole (*No* = 53). This is
379 probably due to the fact that they confer rigidity to the molecule.

380 On the other hand, the presence of nitrogen in aromatic rings (*NA* variable) is
381 also important to favour enantioresolution on *Am3* (e.g., for disopyramide (*No* = 1),
382 myclobutanil (*No* = 16), penconazole (*No* = 17), pantoprazole (*No* = 52), rabeprazole
383 (*No* = 53), oppositely to *Am1* column. In the basic aromatic rings (e.g. pyridinic rings),
384 in which the nitrogen atom is not connected to a hydrogen atom, the lone pair of
385 electrons is not part of the aromatic system and it is responsible for the basicity of these

386 nitrogenous bases, similar to the nitrogen atom in amines. Therefore, they are hydrogen
387 bonding acceptors. In the non-basic rings, in which the nitrogen atom is connected to a
388 hydrogen atom, the lone pair of electrons of the nitrogen atom is delocalised and
389 contributes to the aromatic π -electron system favouring selector-selectand π - π
390 interactions. The combination of these interactions together with the formation of a
391 Lewis adduct between the aromatic amines (Lewis bases) and the chlorine atom in 3-
392 position of the phenylcarbamate moiety in *Am3* column (Lewis acid) and/or between the
393 aromatic amines and the acidic proton of the carbamate moiety of *Am3*, which
394 hydrogen-bond donor character is exalted by the 3-chloro substitution, could explain the
395 opposite selectivity to *Am1* column. Disopyramide (*No* = 1), myclobutanil (*No* = 16)
396 and penconazole (*No* = 17) are examples of aromatic amines exhibiting this opposite
397 enantioselectivity between *Am1* and *Am3* columns (see Table 1).

398 4. Conclusions

399 In this paper, the resolution ability of three commercial amylose-based chiral
400 stationary phases (*Am1*, *Am2* and *Am3*) is studied using acetonitrile/ammonium
401 bicarbonate mobile phases compatible with MS detection. On the other hand, maximum
402 retention factor are set to 15, so the chiral chromatographic methods developed are
403 directly transferable to routine work. Studies are conducted for 53 structurally unrelated
404 chiral compounds.

405 In the experimental conditions assayed which include mobile phases with a
406 water content in the range 20-90% (v/v), for all the compounds studied and CSPs,
407 typical chromatographic reversed phase behaviour was observed. On the other hand,
408 resolution improved as the percentage of acetonitrile in the mobile phase decreased
409 (retention increased) for most compounds. However, for some compounds better
410 resolutions were achieved when using higher percentages of acetonitrile in the mobile
411 phase for all the CSPs studied.

412 Hydrophobicity of compounds was an important property determining their
413 retention in *Am1* and in a lesser extent in *Am2*. In contrast, retention of analytes was
414 found to be independent of their hydrophobicity in *Am3* column.

415 *Am1* and *Am3* CSPs allowed baseline resolution for a similar number of
416 compound. Nevertheless, differences in chiral selectivities between both columns were
417 observed. *Am2* provided the worst results, although its selectivity is also complementary
418 to the other CSPs.

419 FS-DPLS1 modelling for 58 structural variables provided reduced set of
420 variables with positive and negative contributions for categorical enantioresolution in

421 *Am1* and *Am3* CSPs. For a given compound in a given CSP, the balance of such
422 contributions determines enantioresolution in that CSP.

423 For *Am1* and *Am3* CSPs, the presence of carbonyl groups linked to the chiral
424 centre ($C^*C=O$ variable) as well as the presence of aromatic bonds (*Abc* variable) are of
425 great importance in the enantioresolution process. This suggests that selector-selectand
426 π - π and hydrogen-bond interactions could play determinant role. In the case of *Am1*, the
427 position and nature of the substituents in the aromatic ring can favour or disfavour
428 enantioresolution. For *Am1* column, the presence of a ternary amine (hydrogen-bond
429 acceptor) in an aliphatic cyclic group also favours enantioresolution (*NRc* variable).

430 For *Am3* column the presence of fused rings (*frc* variable) also improves
431 resolution. This is probably due to the fact that they confer rigidity to the molecule.

432 On the other hand, the presence of nitrogen in aromatic rings (*NA* variable) is
433 also important for enantioselectivity. Although, this variable presents an opposite effect
434 for each column, i.e. favourable for *Am3* and unfavourable for *Am1*. The combination of
435 selector-selectand π - π and hydrogen bonding interactions together with the formation of
436 a Lewis adduct between the aromatic amines (Lewis bases) and the chlorine atom in 3-
437 position of the phenylcarbamate moiety in *Am3* column (Lewis acid) and/or between the
438 aromatic amines and the acidic proton of the carbamate moiety of *Am3*, which
439 hydrogen-bond donor character is exalted by the 3-chloro substitution could explain this
440 opposite selectivity to *Am1* column.

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447

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576

577 **Figure captions**

578 **Figure 1.** Resolution values, (\blacktriangle) R_s , and retention factors, k , for the less (\bullet) and the
579 most retained enantiomer (\blacksquare) versus the percentage of acetonitrile (ACN , %) in the
580 mobile phase. **(A)** Rabeprazole in $Am2$ and **(B)** brompheniramine in $Am1$. See further
581 details in section 2.3.

582

583 **Figure 2.** Representation of the logarithm of retention factor for less retained
584 enantiomer ($\log k_1$) versus the logarithm of the distribution coefficient ($\log D$) at $pH = 8$
585 for the CSPs studied: **(A)** $Am1$, **(B)** $Am2$ and **(C)** $Am3$. The mobile phases used for this
586 data were 5 mM ammonium bicarbonate ($pH\ 8$)/acetonitrile (50/50, v/v) for $Am1$ and 5
587 mM ammonium bicarbonate buffer ($pH\ 8$)/acetonitrile (40/60, v/v) for $Am2$ and $Am3$.

588

589 **Figure 3.** Feature selection progress in the case of $Am1$ column. (\circ) Discriminant
590 distance (dD); (\times) Discriminant distance in cross-validation (dD_{cv}). A discriminant
591 distance above zero (dotted horizontal line) implies fully discrimination between
592 classes. Elimination of 35 variables (vertical dashed line) provides a suitable DPLS1
593 model (with 22 remaining variables), providing $dD > 0$ (the highest value during the FS-
594 DPLS1 process), which suggests acceptable descriptive ability.

595

596 **Figure 4.** Regression coefficients obtained by FS-DPLS1 for: **(A)** $Am1$ and **(B)** $Am3$.
597 See section 2.4 for further details.